

SPACE ENVIRONMENTAL EFFECTS ON POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITE
MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Results are presented on the behaviour of a variety of fibre reinforced polymer matrix composites that comprised the UTIAS experiment on the NASA-LDEF satellite. LDEF was launched in April 1984 and retrieved in January 1990, thus providing a space exposure of about 70 months. The UTIAS experiment consisted of 62 tubes, a stainless steel calibration tube and 45 flat samples. A data acquisition system was incorporated to monitor 16 channels of strain and temperature, every 16 hours for the first year in orbit. Data is presented for several epoxy matrix composites with carbon, boron and Kevlar® reinforcements. Results to date show clearly the effect of outgassing on the dimensional changes of these materials and the corresponding coefficients of thermal expansion. In addition, the erosion of these materials due to atomic oxygen is demonstrated as a function of the orientation of the samples relative to the incident O atoms.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Polymer; Space Environment Effects; Evaluation; Properties

1. INTRODUCTION

The Long Duration Exposure Facility (LDEF) was launched by NASA in April 1984 and retrieved in January 1990. The purpose of the satellite was to provide an opportunity to study the space environment and its effects on materials. LDEF is an aluminum cylinder, 10 m long with a 12 sided polygon cross-section of about 4.5 m diameter that accommodated 72 experiment trays around the circumference and 14 trays on the two ends (see Figure 1).

UTIAS provided the sole Canadian experiment which consisted of a variety of epoxy matrix composites with graphite, boron and Kevlar® fibre reinforcements (Figure 2). The purpose of this experiment was to determine the changes in physical, chemical and mechanical properties of these materials due to prolonged exposure to the space environment. Factors that can cause

FIGURE 1. Location of UTIAS composite materials experiment on LDEF.

material degradation include thermal-vacuum cycling, solar radiation, high energy electrons, protons and micrometeoroids (as well as man-made debris in space) and erosion due to atomic oxygen.

Although no on-board power and telemetry were provided, UTIAS designed, constructed and space qualified a data acquisition system to monitor 16 channels of "strain" and "temperature," every 16 hours for the first year in orbit. The magnetic tape cassette-based unit functioned flawlessly and yielded 557 data points (Figure 2). The experiment included a stainless steel calibration tube, 62 composite tubes and 45 coupons. It was located at 90° to the leading edge of LDEF (see Figure 1) which, by NASA estimates, was yawed about 10° relative to the velocity vector. This provided enhanced exposure to atomic oxygen, resulting in a total fluence of $\sim 4 \times 10^{20}$ atoms/cm² (Reference 1). The following report presents results from our LDEF experiment.

2. THERMAL RESPONSE AND OUTGASSING

A listing of the composite materials that were monitored over the first 371 days after deployment of LDEF is given in Table 1. Both temperature and strain [using conventional thermal foil gauges (MM-STG-50C) and strain gauges (MM-WK-13-250BG-350)] were recorded to assess the thermal response changes due to space exposure. A stainless steel tube was employed as a means of calibrating the gauge system and determining if any deterioration occurred over the measurement lifetime.

FIGURE 2.
Photographs of UTIAS
experiment.

Figures 3 and 4 present the temperature-time and strain-time histories, respectively, for the stainless steel tube. It is interesting to note that there is no significant strain change with time at a given temperature for the stainless steel. This demonstrates that no degradation in the gauge measuring system has occurred, and no significant outgassing or dimensional changes have taken place. Note that the low frequency variations in the thermal/time response correspond to orbital precession of the satellite, and the higher frequency effects are associated with different locations on the orbit (see Reference 2 for analysis).

Using this data, one can construct a thermal distortion vs. temperature curve for stainless steel (Figure 5). One can see that all the test data collapsed to a single straight line, yielding a slope [i.e., coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of $\sim 18 \times 10^{-6}/K$ which matches the ground-based value for this material (see Table 1). Subsequent tests in a ground-based thermal-vacuum chamber yielded the same CTE (Table 1), thus demonstrating that no deterioration of the measuring system took place throughout the six years of elapsed time.

TABLE 1. SUMMARY OF LDEF COMPOSITE MATERIALS THERMAL-VACUUM DATA — UTIAS EXPERIMENT

Material Type	Configuration	t_0^* (days)	Strain Gauge Angle ($^\circ$)	Permanent Dimensional Change (Δ strain, 10^{-6})	Ambient CTE** ($10^{-6}/K$)	Space CTE† ($10^{-6}/K$)	Thermal-Vacuum CTE†† ($10^{-6}/K$)
Stainless Steel (Calibration)	Tube	—	0	—	17.71	18.0	18.0
Graphite/Epoxy 934/T300	Flat $4 \times 0^\circ$	40	0	-1200	2.38	5.99	4.50
			90		26.46	25~27	28.98
Kevlar/Epoxy SP-328	Tube $4 \times 90^\circ$	120	90	-2800	61.02	54~99	63.54
			0		0.18	1.28	1.13
Graphite/Epoxy SP288/T300	Tube $4 \times 0^\circ$	40	90	-900	26.28	24.5~25.7	27.72
			0		1.75~2.83	-2.05~5.99	6.75
Graphite/Epoxy 5208/T300	Tube $4 \times 90^\circ$	80	90	-1550	28.10	22.5~27.5	28.98
Boron/Epoxy SP-290	Tube $4 \times \pm 30^\circ$	85	30	+150	2.83	3.01~4.0	0.79~3.6
			60		21.06	13.5~20.0	22.86

* Time to outgas

** Coefficient of thermal expansion at atmospheric pressure prior to launch

† Measured in space environment on LDEF during first 371 days in orbit

†† Measured in laboratory thermal-vacuum test facility (22 hrs. @ 10-5 torr, 233K to 339K) after 2,114 days in orbit and 184 days at ambient conditions

FIGURE 3. Temperature vs. time in orbit for stainless steel specimen.

FIGURE 4. Thermal strain vs. time for stainless steel specimen.

FIGURE 5. Thermal response for stainless steel.

Figure 6 presents the thermal response curve for a graphite/epoxy 934/T300 laminate. Note the larger amplitudes in the thermal response compared to those observed for stainless steel. This can be attributed to the much lower *thermal mass* of the composite samples relative to that for the stainless steel tube. Of particular importance is the *outgassing time* (t_0) and associated *dimensional change* (De) summarized in Table 1. The corresponding strain/time measurements in the 0° (A) and 90° (B) directions are given in Figure 7. From these curves one can construct the strain vs. temperature response in the 0° (A) and 90° (B) directions, as shown in Figure 8.

FIGURE 6. Temperature vs. time for graphite/epoxy laminate (934/T300).

It is interesting to compare the *initial* and *final* asymptotic curves. For the 0° configuration, a slight shift in the CTE is evident. It is also clear that it took about 40 days for this material to outgas and asymptote to a constant CTE, as can be seen in the 90° sample curves. Figure 9 presents a plot of the actual change in strain (δ) for the 90° laminate as a function of exposure time in the space environment. It can be seen that in the 90° direction, a permanent dimensional change results from outgassing which amounts to $\sim 1200 \times 10^{-6}$ for this material. Note that a post-flight measurement of the 90° strain at ambient temperature showed a recovery in the dimensional change. This reflects re-absorption of moisture after retrieval of LDEF. Subsequent thermal-vacuum tests* also demonstrated these effects due to outgassing. A comparison of the CTE values measured in space (after 371 days) with those observed in simulator tests (after 2114 days in orbit and 184 days at ambient conditions) shows reasonable agreement (Table 1). This indicates that no substantial degradation in material thermal response has occurred, other than that associated with outgassing.

A summary of the outgassing times, dimensional changes and CTE measurements is contained in Table 1 for all the materials investigated. From a design viewpoint, the dimensional changes for the 0° and 90° laminates can be used to predict the D_e for an arbitrary laminate configuration. Clearly, the matrix-dominated properties are most affected by outgassing (i.e., see the 90° results) but it was also found that the angle ply laminate of boron/epoxy underwent a significant D_e change as well. Outgassing can lead to permanent dimensional changes of composite laminates in orbit and must be taken into account in the design of composite structures and joints where dimensional tolerances are critical (e.g., optical systems, truss joints, guidance systems and communication platforms).

*These tests were conducted at the Canadian Communications Research Centre, David Florida Labs., Ottawa, Canada.

FIGURE 7. Thermal strain vs. time for graphite/epoxy laminates in the 0° (A) and 90° (B) directions (934/T300).

3. ATOMIC OXYGEN EROSION

3.1 Flat Laminates All UTIAS composite samples were mounted on the trays with aluminum end fixtures. Because of the location of this experiment and the yaw of LDEF in orbit, it is estimated by NASA that the angle of incidence of the atomic oxygen (AO) was 7~10°. Analysis of the flat laminates has shown that the end tabs provided a shadow region of approximately 5~6 mm (Figure 10).

FIGURE 8. Thermal response measured in the 0° (A) and 90° (B) directions for graphite/epoxy laminates (934/T300).

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) analysis indicates that this area essentially suffered no AO erosion. Beyond this region, however, visual evidence shows significant loss of the outer epoxy layer (Figure 11). The surface morphology is quite different than that observed for epoxy surfaces subject to *normal* (or *ram* direction) oxygen atoms. The *triangular* erosion patterns of Figure 11 result from small angle of incidence AO (relative to the sample plane). This was confirmed by tests run in the UTIAS AO simulator for specimens subject to AO at 90° and 20°

FIGURE 9. Dimensional change with time in space environment for 90° graphite/epoxy laminate (934/T300).

to their plane (Reference 3). At 20°, the triangular patterns were evident in the matrix material. A SEM photograph of the unexposed region B (Figure 11) is shown for comparative purposes (Figure 12).

It was further observed that AO reflected off the cylindrical aluminum end fixtures located below the flat samples, resulting in circular erosion patterns (region C, Figure 10) on the bottom (unexposed) face of the same flat samples. A SEM photograph of this eroded region (Figure 13) exhibited a surface morphology that was quite different than that on the exposed surface (Figure 11). This can be attributed to the non-directionality of the reflected AO and is much more characteristic of *normal incidence* erosion.

Figure 14 presents thickness measurements of the exposed area. It was found that essentially only the surface resin layer was eroded, amounting to approximately 10–14 μm for this particular sample. From Reference 1, the erosion yield for an epoxy material is quoted at $1.7 \times 10^{-24} \text{ cm}^3/\text{atom}$. Hence, for a total AO fluence of $4.1 \times 10^{20} \text{ atoms/cm}^2$ at station D-12, the predicted thickness loss is $\sim 7 \mu\text{m}$.

3.2 Circular Tubes Atomic oxygen erosion of circular tubes has also been investigated. Surface erosion morphologies were observed on the cylinder (Figure 15) similar to the flat sample shown in Figure 11.

The actual thickness profile in the region of maximum erosion is presented in Figure 16. The variation in erosion depth as a function of angular position on the tube's circumference (a) is

FIGURE 10. Photographs of top (exposed) and bottom (unexposed) faces of graphite/epoxy LDEF sample (5208/T300 ($\pm 45^\circ$)₄).

given in Figure 17. From this data one can estimate an average thickness loss in the exposed region of about $80\ \mu\text{m}$, with a maximum reduction of $\sim 160\ \mu\text{m}$ for a $\simeq 15^\circ$ (corresponding to about one ply of material). From Reference 1, the erosion yield for graphite/epoxy laminates is quoted at $2.1\text{--}2.6 \times 10^{-24}\ \text{cm}^3/\text{atom}$. Again, for a fluence of $4.1 \times 10^{20}\ \text{atoms/cm}^2$, the predicted thickness loss would only amount to $9\text{--}11\ \mu\text{m}$. However, since this region was exposed to near "ram" conditions, the quoted fluence (from Reference 1) increases to $1.05 \times 10^{22}\ \text{atoms/cm}^2$. This increases the predicted thickness loss to $220\text{--}270\ \mu\text{m}$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the UTIAS/LDEF composite materials experiment, the following preliminary conclusions can be made:

- (a) outgassing of the polymer matrix composites occurred over periods ranging from 40 to 120 days, depending on the material system;

(x750, 7° tilt)

FIGURE 11. SEM photograph of region A on exposed face of graphite/epoxy flat sample (5208/T300 ($\pm 45^\circ$)₄).

Unexposed Region B
(x750, 7° tilt)

FIGURE 12. SEM photograph of unexposed region B (see Figure 10).

Exposed Region C
(x750, 7° tilt)

FIGURE 13. SEM photograph of exposed region C (see Figure 10).

Effect of Atomic Oxygen Erosion on Graphite/Epoxy LDEF Sample

FIGURE 14. Effect of atomic oxygen erosion on graphite/epoxy LDEF sample.

- (b) significant permanent dimensional changes occurred in the samples due to outgassing, which must be factored into the design of low distortion composite laminates;
- (c) outgassing caused modest changes in CTE, leading to asymptotic values that should be used in the design of 'zero CTE' laminates for space applications;
- (d) low angle of incidence atomic oxygen eroded the composite materials which were located approximately 80° off the ram direction;
- (e) erosion by atomic oxygen of cylindrical tubes caused substantial thickness reductions amounting to about $160\ \mu\text{m}$ over the 70 months in low Earth orbit;
- (f) micrometeoroid/debris impacts can penetrate four ply laminates with substantial rear face spallation damage (see Reference 3).

FIGURE 15. SEM photograph ($\times 750$) of erosion region on graphite/epoxy tube (4 ply 90° , 934/T300)

FIGURE 16. Region of maximum erosion ($\alpha \approx 15^\circ$) of graphite/epoxy tube wall (934/T300; 4 ply 90°).

FIGURE 17. Erosion profile of graphite/epoxy circular tube due to atomic oxygen.

5. REFERENCES

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